

Conditional Probability $P(p/x)$ and Energy Variance at X for Quantum Bound States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 29, 2022

If one defines a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x)$ =wavefunction then $\sum_p P(p/x) = 1$, but $P(p/x)$ is complex and its real and imaginary parts may have positive and negative values at different x points. Nevertheless one may establish an average energy conservation equation with the same E_n (energy of the n th level) at each x which mimics classical mechanics for all n values. This equation is identical to the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

If one treats $P(p/x)$ as a distribution and obtains an average E_n that holds at each x point like temperature holds at each x for a statistical mechanical gas, one should be able to calculate the variance at x as well i.e. $\sum_p P(p/x) [\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) - E_n] [\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) - E_n] = \text{Var}(E(x))$. We examine this value for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls and for a harmonic oscillator. One may then average $\text{Var}(E_n(x))$. We also consider implications on entropy.

Conditional Probability

If $\exp(ipx)$ describes a free quantum particle in terms of a kind of unusual probability that has the property that $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ i.e. that a momentum impulse of p may be delivered at any x with the same probability or one may find the particle at any point x with the same probability, then one may consider a statistical distribution of such $\exp(ipx)$'s namely:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{with } \sum_p P(p/x) = 1$$

$P(p/x)$ is unusual in that it is complex and its real and complex parts may have positive and negative values at different x points. Using $P(p/x)$ to write an average conservation of energy law at each x point one has:

$$\{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \frac{p^2}{2m} \} / \{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

The first term is identical to the classical kinetic energy of a particle at x for any n level. It is nevertheless an average of $\exp(ipx)$ and the experimental argument seems to be that various p values may be observed if the particle is knocked out of a bound state. In fact $a^*(p)a(p)$ is the probability of finding a particle with momentum p with no knowledge of its x position.

((2)) suggests one should also be able to calculate an energy variance at each x i.e.

$$\text{Var}(E(x)) = \sum_p P(p/x) [\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) - E_n] [\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) - E_n] \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Var}(E(x)) = \sum_p P(p/x) \frac{p^4}{(4mm)} - E_n E_n + V(x)V(x) + 2V(x) KE_{\text{classical}}(x) \quad ((4a))$$

Using the time-independent Schrodinger equation one has

$$\sum_p P(p/x) \frac{p^4}{(4mm)} = 1/W_n(x) (-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \{ (E_n - V) W_n \}$$

Thus:

$$\text{Var}(E(x)) = \frac{1}{W_n(x)} \left(-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \{ (E_n - V) W_n \} - (E_n - V(x)) (E_n - V(x)) \right) \quad ((4b))$$

$$\text{Var}(E(x)) = \frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dV(x)}{dx} + \left(\frac{dV}{dx} \right) \frac{1}{m} \frac{dW_n}{dx} / W_n \quad ((4c))$$

It seems in principle that this variance may be nonzero, suggesting that the quantum mechanical E_n average is not the only parameter of interest.

We consider two examples.

Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

Consider infinite potential walls at $x=0$ and $x=L$. Then:

$$W(x) = C_1 \sin(k_n x) \quad \text{where } k_n = n\pi/L \quad ((5))$$

Using ((4)) for an x point within the box one finds that:

$$\text{Var}(E(x)) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

This is an interesting result because according to (1) all values of p are used to construct ((5)). $P(p/x)$, however, is an unusual probability which may have positive and negative values for different p values.

Oscillator

Next consider an oscillator and its $\text{Var}(E(x=0))$ for which $V(x) = .5kx^2$

$$\text{Var}(E(x=0)) = \sum \text{over } p \frac{P(p/x)}{W_n(x)} \left(\frac{p^2}{4m} - E_n \right) - \left(\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} (E_n - .5kx^2) \right) W_n(x) - E_n E_n$$

$$= \frac{k}{2m} \frac{W_n(0)}{W_n(0)} - E_n E_n + (E_n - V(0)) (E_n - V(0)) \frac{W_n(0)}{W_n(0)} = \frac{k}{2m} \quad ((7a))$$

Thus $\text{Var}(E_n(x=0)) = k/2m$ a constant for all n values at $x=0$. The variance, however, is nonzero suggesting that E_n the average energy matches a classical energy, but that there is more occurring.

For any x , the variance is:

$$\text{Var}(E_n(x)) = \frac{k}{2m} + kx \frac{dW_n}{dx} / (m W_n) \quad ((7b))$$

This depends on x and n . For the ground state $W_0 = C_1 \exp(-.5 a x^2)$ where $a = \sqrt{km}$. Then

$$\text{Var}(E_n(x)) = k/2m - \sqrt{km} k x x/m$$

This result becomes larger with x . If one takes an average over all of x , however, using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ the xx term is overwhelmingly damped for large x . Thus it might be better to consider:

$$P(x) \text{Var}(E_n(x)) \text{ where } P(x) = W^*(x)W(x).$$

Variance over all x ?

If one considers $P(p/x)$ as the probability needed to compute $\text{Var}(E(x))$, one may ask: What is the overall variance of x integrated over x ? In such a case, one may integrate over x using $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ as a weight.

$$\int dx P(x) \text{Var}(E(x)) = \int dx P(x) \left\{ \frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dV(x)}{dx} + \left(\frac{dV(x)}{dx} \right)^2 \frac{1}{m} \frac{dW_n/dx}{W_n} \right\} \quad ((8))$$

Consider ((8)) for an oscillator for which $V(x) = .5kx^2$

$$\text{Var}(E \text{ over all } x) = \int W_n W_n \left\{ \frac{k}{2m} + \left(\frac{k}{m} \right) x \frac{dW_n/dx}{W_n} \right\} = \frac{k}{2m} + \frac{k}{m} \int dx x W_n \frac{dW_n/dx}{W_n}$$

Using: $\int dx \frac{d}{dx} (x W_n W_n) = 0 = \int W_n W_n dx + \int x dx 2 W_n dx W_n$ one has:

$$\text{Var}(E_n \text{ over all } x) = \frac{k}{2m} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{k}{m} \right) \quad ((9)) \text{ which is a constant for all } n.$$

Thus the average variance of E_n does not seem to be linked to classical mechanics i.e. ((9)) is a constant independent of n so for large n it is the same as for small.

Entropy Considerations

Given a variance, a certain probability has been used which may also be utilized in Shannon's entropy equation, it seems. For the case of $\text{Var}(E \text{ over all } x)$, the probability used is $P(x)P(p/x)$ which is the usual probability also used for expectation values of operators. In previous notes we have seen that this leads to a Shannon's entropy of:

$$S = .5S_p + .5S_x \text{ where } S_p = - \int dp a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\} \text{ and } S_x = - \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*W\}. \quad ((9))$$

It seems that for a variance at x one might be able to define an entropy at point x . In this case, only the probability $P(p/x)$ is used leading to a Shannon's entropy of:

$$S(x) = -\ln(W) - mx \left\{ \frac{-dW/dx}{Wm} \right\} + \frac{1}{W} \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \exp(ipx) a(p) \ln(a(p)) \right\} \quad ((10))$$

For a bound state with a certain symmetry $\exp(ipx)$ may be replaced with $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. The second term is $-mx$ multiplied by the average momentum at x , but overall ((10)) is not a particularly simple formula. The $\text{Var}(E_n(x))$, however, is also unusual and one might wish to consider $P(x)\text{Var}(E_n(x))$ to avoid $\text{Var}(E_n(x))$ becoming overwhelmingly large as in the ground state oscillator case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in quantum mechanics a momentum distribution is used i.e. $W(x)$ = wavefunction = $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. E_n in the time-dependent Schrodinger equation seems to be an average energy, while for a classical situation it is considered an exact. If one uses the conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$ then $\text{Var}(E_n(x)) = \sum_p P(p/x) [p^2/2m + V(x) - E_n]^2$ $[p^2/2m + V(x) - E_n] = 1/2m d/dx dV(x)/dx + (dV/dx) 1/m dWn/dx / Wn$

where $V(x)$ is the potential. This variance may be multiplied by $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and integrated over x to give an averaged variance. We consider the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls and an oscillator. For the former, the variance is 0 for all n .

We also argue that if one uses $P(p/x)$ to calculate $\text{Var}(E_n(x))$ and $P(p/x)P(x)$ to find an average variance, there should be corresponding Shannon's entropies. We find: $S(x) = -\ln(W) - mx \{-dW/dx / Wm\} + 1/W \{ \sum_p \exp(ipx) a(p) \ln(a(p)) \}$ for $P(p/x)$ and $S = .5Sp + .5Sx$ for $P(p/x)P(x)$ where Sp uses $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ and Sx uses $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$. It is not clear if $S(x)$ is particularly useful because as seen for the ground state oscillator it corresponds to $\text{Var}(E_n(x))$ which goes to infinite for large x while $P(x)\text{Var}(E_n(x))$ tends to 0.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box